

Instructional Media Methods for Use in Learning of English Language in Public Secondary Schools in Kakamega East Sub-Country, Kenya

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Abstract

Teachers have embraced media that engage and empower learners during learning process. Instructional media methods enhance interaction, collaboration, problem-based learning and peer – learning in education. They produce positive learning outcomes due to their interactive nature. However, it was not clear whether learners had an education on interpretation and understanding of media use in learning process. The research specifically focused on lesson plans checking and certification, teaching and learning strategies used with media, incorporation of radio programs in teaching/learning and instructional media methods in learning process. A specific objective of the study was to examine instructional media methods for use in learning of English language in public secondary schools in Kakamega East Sub-County, Kenya. The study used components of Generic Model proposed by Wang (2008) and adopted descriptive survey design. The findings of the study revealed that teacher – learner interactive method and learner - centred method incorporated with media improved learning outcomes. The study recommended that school administrators should emphasize use of media in learning process. The research provided additional information in formulating policies which enhance integration of instructional media in learning process.

Keywords: *Instructional media methods, use.*

Acronyms: ETQ - English Teacher's Questionnaire, PQ - Principal's Questionnaire, LQ - Learner's Questionnaire, DVDs - Digital Video Disks, CDs - Compact Disks, ICT - Information Communication Technology, IEP - Individualized Education Program, PLE - Playful Learning Environment.

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Introduction

Instructional media methods involve use of media such as phone, camera, computer, projector, DVDs/CDs, flash discs, memory cards, external hard discs and television (TV) in learning process. Instructional media improve interaction during learning process (International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA), 2015). The study of Herodotou, Sharples, Gared, Kukulska – Hulme, Rienties and

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Denise (2019) indicated that the following teaching methods enhanced interactive learning: playful learning, teach-back, placed – based learning, exploration and dynamic assessment during which teachers helped learners to identify and overcome learning difficulties. The approaches are supported by effective educational theories such as experimental, inquiry, discovery and self regulated learning. All of which engaged learners. They posted desirable learning outcomes in both the cognitive and emotional domain. Instructional media teaching methods have shifted education towards a student – centred learning environment. The research targeted innovative pedagogies of the future thus an integrated framework was developed to select the pedagogies. Another study of Aija and Inga (2012) ranked teaching strategies as follows: lectures (5%), reading (10%), demonstrations (30%), group discussions (50%), practical activities (75%), peer – teaching and immediate use of knowledge in practice (90%). Therefore, learner focused teaching strategies produced high level learning outcomes. It showed that interactive teaching methods raised student’s interest in learning process. Hence, interaction formed cooperation between learners’ efforts. Their study suggested that Information Communication Technology (ICT) teaching – learning methods made Mathematics blossom.

Traditional classroom lectures are now fading into the past. New teaching methodologies have emerged or new versions of old teaching strategies are being implemented into 21st Century education. Today’s teachers have embraced new technologies that help to engage and empower learners. Moreover, instructional media methods integrated with a Playful Learning Environment (PLE) produced positive learning outcomes. These observations focused on teaching methods for the 21st Century (Cox, 2023). The research of Carolyn, Timothy, Homer, Tse – Yang and Yi – Hsuan (2017) asserted that interactive educational methods connected learning to needs of learners. Collaborative learning strategies offered the teacher with aids to produce desirable learning outcomes. Thus, participation helped students to realise tasks and provided cooperation among teachers and students. This report focused on effects of teaching strategies on student achievement in science in United States (US). It was Meta – analysis of US research published from 1980 to 2004.

Significantly, various traditional teaching methods have remained important for teachers of English Language. However, instructional media enabled the teacher to modify teaching-learning strategies in order to create student – centred learning environment instead of the traditional teacher centred which has persisted for long. Teacher-student interactive (mixed) and learner-centred methods generally drew on learning theories which suggested that learners should play an active role in learning process. Specifically, the study: examined instructional media methods for use in learning of English language in public secondary schools in Kakamega East Sub – County, Kenya. The key question this study aimed to answer was how well are teachers and learners prepared on use of instructional media methods in learning of English language?

Methodology

The study population consisted of 23 principals, 46 teachers of English and 1500 Form Two students. A sample of 20 principals and 40 teachers of English was selected using saturated sampling method while simple random sampling technique was used to select 500 Form Two students. Piloting of instruments was done on 10% of the population. Research tools involved questionnaires and observation schedule. The main data collection instrument was questionnaire; one administered to principals, another to teachers of English and finally to Form Two students. Observation schedule confirmed the results from the questionnaires. Quantitative data was collected from the closed questionnaire items which were tallied and presented using frequency counts, percentages and means. Qualitative data was transcribed and organised into categories and themes based on the study objective. This study used test – retest (coefficient of stability) method to estimate the degree of reliability of the instruments. The study relied on face validity procedures using three sets of experts. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages and means).

Results and Discussions

This section highlighted on lesson plans checking and certification, how instructional media assisted teachers in realization of lesson objectives, radio programs pre-teaching activities, teaching strategies used with media in the classrooms, learning strategies incorporated with instructional media and instructional media methods in learning process.

Before teachers begin to plan, they must understand how their students learn with instructional media. Through this, learners would learn to match instructional media to the intended learning and how it is related to other key language skills. Serious planning for teaching involved preparation of Schemes of Work (SOW) followed by lesson plan. Lesson plan provide a tentative format of upcoming learning experience to achieve short term and long term objectives. It makes learning a systematic process.

Principal's Questionnaire (PQ) sought to find out how often principals checked and certified lesson plans during and after learning process. The findings summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Extent Lesson Plans Checked and Certified

n= 20 Principals

Extent Lesson Plans Checked and Certified	Number of Principals (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Daily	1	5
Weekly	2	10
Fortnightly	3	15
Monthly	11	55
Never at all	3	15
Total	20	100.00

Table 1 revealed that 17 (30%) principals checked and certified lesson plans daily 1 (5%), weekly 2 (10%) and fortnightly 3 (15%). Therefore, lesson plans were insufficiently checked and certified in schools. They must be checked and certified daily to ensure that learners learn from the curriculum and content of the key learning areas. This would assist teachers to manage learners' boredom through planning adequately in advance.

Significantly, teachers used word processors in preparation of SOW and lesson plans. A well done lesson plan helped the teacher to assemble teaching/learning media and evaluate pedagogic and learning activities effectively. It presented concepts and skills in a systematic manner using appropriate strategies to achieve the stated lesson outcomes. Although, where little planning occurred; the results indicated that learner's work was often unfocused and resulted in low attainment in the classroom. The above mentioned results were in line with Hilkeмейjer (2022) observations though he focused on planning for ICT use for teaching and learning in the curriculum.

The study also expressed that lesson plans developed by teachers who had received adequate in-service training/pre-service training in media incorporation played an important role in the curriculum. It was noted that these teachers reflected on media integration skills appropriately when planning for a lesson. This ensured that knowledge obtained during in-service training/pre-service training was used to transform education from theory to practice. These results agreed with Mumcu (2017) study. Contrarily, Mumcu's research focused on planning for integration of ICT into learning and teaching process.

English Teacher's Questionnaire (ETQ) found out from teachers extent to which instructional media assisted them in realization of lesson objectives. Results were summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Extent Instructional Media Assisted in Realisation of Lesson Objectives

n= 40 Teachers of English

Instructional Media	Great Extent (GE)		Moderate Extent (ME)		Lesser Extent (LE)	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Computer	21	53	9	23	5	13
Internet	22	55	11	27	4	10
Smart boards	0	0	6	14	0	0
Power point	4	11	15	37	3	8
E-images	1	3	7	17	0	0

Table 2 showed that 21 (53%), 9 (23%) and 5 (13%) teachers agreed that computer assisted them in realization of lesson objectives greatly, moderately and lesser extent respectively. Teachers also suggested that internet assisted great extent (55%) moderate extent 11 (27%) and lesser extent 4 (10%) in realization of lesson objectives. Conversely, both smart boards 6 (14%) and e-images 7 (17%) assisted teachers in realization of lesson objectives at moderate extent. Smart boards, power point and e-images inadequately assisted in realisation of lesson objectives. This was attributed to teacher’s limited pedagogical skills which had direct influence on innovatory use of instructional media in the classroom.

Radio Program (as a supplement to classroom teaching) possibilities are almost unlimited in education. Significantly, PQ sought to find out how often teachers of English incorporated radio programs in their lesson plans. The findings summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Radio Programs Pre – Teaching Activities

n=20 Principals

Extent of Incorporation of Radio Programs	Number of Principals (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Very often	3	15
Often	8	40
Fairly often	5	25
Rarely often	3	15
Never at all	1	5
Total	20	100.0

Table 3 depicted that 3 (15%), 8 (40%), 5 (25), 3 (15%) and 1 (5%) principals indicated that teachers incorporated radio programs in their lesson plans very often, often, fairly often, rarely often and never at all respectively. Principals showed that teachers adequately incorporated radio programs in their lesson plans. They greatly engaged learners during teaching and learning process. Radio broadcast compelled learners to support the sound message by using their imagination. Audio software contained alternatives such as play, stop and record which were at the disposal of the teacher. It enabled teachers and learners to access the best of the world’s store of knowledge. The above observation concurred with Aliza (2006) and Mwara (2011) studies. Mwara’s study focused on factors influencing use of radio in teaching and learning in secondary schools; case study of Starehe District in Nairobi County, Kenya whereas, Aliza investigated effectiveness of radio as an educational medium in the curriculum.

Respondents suggested that learners participated actively in learning process when radio programmes were incorporated in lesson plans. It was clear that teachers presented information that actively engaged learners so as to apply knowledge learnt afterwards. The radio program also solved various problems in schools such as shortage of good textbooks, inadequate instructional media and lack of competent/experienced teachers in areas such as pronunciation.

Teachers did the following to utilize radio lessons in the classrooms, they: (i). planned integration of the schedule broadcasting programme with their classroom teaching, (ii) prepared their students adequately to get knowledge and experiences properly imparted through a radio broadcast, and (iii) provided follow

up programmes after a radio broadcast in the classrooms. Further, teachers sent Short Message Service (SMS) to inform parents/guardians about radio programmes available for their children so as to engage them at home.

The study also revealed that teachers had heavy workload, large number of learners in the classrooms (over-enrolment of students in classrooms), inadequate broadcast timetables/teachers' guides and insufficient pedagogical skills in utilization of radio programmes. This limited the use of radio programmes in the curriculum. The abovementioned observations were in tandem with Weru (2018) study. Conversely, he investigated utilization of radio programmes produced by Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD); case study of public primary schools in Ruiru Sub-County, Kenya. Lastly, he collected data using questionnaires only.

Teaching strategies are tools for varying pedagogic approach. They are used to help learners to: check their understanding, consolidate their learning and become independent in education. In a lesson a teacher can use many different teaching strategies with different end goals. Every learner is unique however teachers should use a combination of teaching strategies supported with instructional media to address their varying learning styles and academic capabilities. Consequently, this makes classrooms to be dynamic and motivational environments for both the teacher and learner.

The most effective way to develop learner's media capabilities is to provide them with meaningful activities embedded in purposeful subject – related contexts. ETQ sought to find out teaching strategies used with media in learning of English language. The results were shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Teaching Strategies Used with Media in the Classrooms

n=40 Teachers of English

Teaching Strategies used with Media	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentages (%)
Collaborative learning strategies	25	63
Inquiry – based learning	24	60
Differentiation	25	62
Group discussions	30	75
Cooperative learning	27	67
Peer-teaching	36	90
Effective Questioning techniques	25	63
Metacognition	17	43
Gamification	29	73
Convergent and Divergent thinking	25	63
Project – based learning	27	67
Experiential learning	25	63
Problem – based learning	26	65
Reciprocal teaching	24	60
Culturally responsive teaching	24	61
Interdisciplinary teaching	28	71
Behaviour management strategy	32	80
Classroom management strategy	33	83
Response to Intervention (RTI)	32	81
Practical activities	30	75
Immediate use of knowledge in practice	35	88
Demonstrations	30	75
Role play	33	83
Socratic seminars	28	71
Mnemonic devices	32	80
Virtual field trip	28	71

Hands on activities	36	90
Guided reading	26	65
Goal setting	32	81
Mind mapping	32	80
Debate	36	90
Cue cards	12	30
Group investigation	24	60
Word walls	28	71
Think-pair-share	30	75

From Table 4, respondents identified that introduction of media in education has led to development of learner-centred teaching strategies such as: collaborative learning (63%), group discussions (75%), cooperative learning (67%), gamification (73%), convergent and divergent thinking (63%), project – based learning (67%), experimental learning (63%), peer – teaching (90%), inquiry – based learning (60%), problem – based learning (65%), reciprocal teaching (60%), culturally responsive teaching (61%) and interdisciplinary teaching (71%) which produced positive learning outcomes in the curriculum. These strategies were considered effective since they did not centralize the flow of knowledge from the teacher to the learner. It was clear that teachers made use of learning media which engaged most of the senses. Significantly, teachers chose teaching strategy most suitable to: the topic being studied, the level of expertise of the learner and the stage in their learning journey.

Other learner-centred teaching strategies included role play (83%), Socratic seminars (71%), virtual field trip (71%), hands-on-activities (90%), mind mapping (80%), debate (90%), think-pair-share (75%) and group investigation (60%). These student led strategies sharpened questioning, critical thinking and dialogue skills amongst learners. An effective teacher required the implementation of creative and innovative teaching strategies in order to meet learners’ individual needs. Therefore, learners were not just given facts; they were led to discover them on their own.

It was noted that teachers posed thought – provoking questions which inspired learners to think for themselves and made them independent learners. Learners also asked questions and investigated ideas using instructional media. This enabled learners to improve their problem – solving skills which enabled them to gain a deeper understanding of academic concepts. This collaborative learning helped learners to think and promoted active participation in the learning process.

Further, teachers used differentiation strategy to allocate tasks based on learners’ abilities; thus no one was left behind in learning process. They were cognizant of the different learning needs of their learners. Classroom activities were assigned according to students’ unique learning needs which meant that individual with higher academic capabilities were stretched and those who were struggling were given the appropriate support. This strategy enabled learners to learn without stigma; it involved all learners in learning process. This strategy showed how teachers reacted to the diverse learning styles in every classroom with adjusted content and processes. Learners felt that they were capable of achieving success. This ensured multi-ability learning in the curriculum.

Moreover, Table 4 indicated that teachers implemented behaviour management strategy by ensuring all students have an equal chance of reaching their full potential. For instance, disruptive classrooms did not encourage productive learning environment. Consequently, teachers developed an atmosphere of mutual respect through a combination of discipline and reward which benefitted both them and learners. However, teachers reported a lack of professional development support on improvement of classroom management strategies. This has led to frustration for teachers of language.

Respondents also suggested that Response to Intervention (RTI) strategy focused on early and continuous identification, assessment and assistance for learners with learning or behaviour needs. In addition, it involved small group or individual intervention that quickly addressed trouble spots in teaching and learning process. Teachers also contacted parents to discuss one-to-one support. It was best used as part of general classroom management plan. Furthermore, Cox (2023) identified that trauma – informed teaching approach recognizes and understands the effects that trauma has on learner’s learning

and behaviour. The respondents underscored that this approach implemented strategies that involved creating safe and supportive learning environment, thus enabled students to heal and thrive. Teachers implemented strategies for their learner's well being and success by offering support services. Teachers learnt how to communicate with students who were managing a crisis and being informed in trauma – informed care and principles.

Reciprocal teaching strategy was used by teachers to involve learners in reading and made them excited to learn. This strategy turned even the most reluctant reader into ardent reader. Further, teachers used experiential learning strategy to counter student disengagement. It involved learners in the learning process. It also provided learners with new ways of learning to help them stay focused hence learnt dynamically and faster.

Findings showed that teachers used inquiry – based learning strategy in classrooms extensively. They guided learners through questions. The respondents identified four main types of inquiry - based learning: confirmation inquiry (learners were given a question along with a way to answer), structured inquiry (an open question and investigation methods were used), guided inquiry (learners worked from an open question to design investigation methods) and in open inquiry (learners developed original questions that they answered through their own methods).

The teachers established that project – based learning strategy was an open – ended which enabled students to engage in group work to find their own way to the solution. As a result, it was used to immerse learners fully in an authentic and nuanced problem that had real – life implication. Accordingly, peer – teaching strategy was used to develop learner's reasoning and critical thinking skills. The strategy involved the following practices: explaining to students how to give feedback and providing written prompts to guide discussions. It improved self – esteem and interpersonal skills amongst learners.

Teachers encouraged learners to develop creative and critical thinking skills through interdisciplinary teaching strategy. This strategy was used to draw information from a number of different academic disciplines as they solved real – world problems. In the classroom environment, the strategy involved collaboration with other teachers. The strategy used activities such as news analysis and historical pen pals (which involved creative writing), hot seating sessions (students took a role of a historical figure and wrote about challenges he/she faced to the classroom).

Respondents used culturally responsive teaching strategy to link content with student's contemporary and ancestral cultures. Moreover, teachers explained how a topic was related to different cultures and as a result this made the classroom a place where all students felt empowered - it was suitably used during Oral Literature lessons.

In divergent thinking strategy, teachers required students to start with one prompt, and then think critically about it to diverge towards distinct answers. Contrarily, convergent thinking was used to understand how separate pieces of information were used to reach one solution. It was used to answer questions that required a limited range of skills and knowledge (such as multiple choice questions). Mainly, convergent and divergent thinking are essential skills in English language.

Respondents suggested that think-pair-share strategy taught students to share ideas with classmates and built oral communication skills. It engages students in comprehending the reading material. Think-pair-share strategy starts with a solo approach whereby each student quietly has to reflect on a question. Next, they pair up and share their thoughts before enlightening the whole class with their ideas. Lastly but not least, Socratic seminars strategy served as a platform for student – led discussions which sharpened learner's critical thinking skills. They engaged learners in formal discussion and require active listening. It requires learners to think critically about the question posed and about the quality of discussion. Students in the second group gain experience offering constructive feedback to their peers. The above mentioned results concurred with Kampen (2021) and Anantha (2021) observations. Anantha's observation focused on most effective teaching strategies used in schools while Kampen's study targeted teaching strategies and techniques for 2021 learning in schools.

In conclusion, teachers of English noted that the most effective approach to implementing teaching strategies is to customize them to meet learners' needs.

ETQ sought to find out from teachers on learning strategies used with instructional media in English language. The results were summed up in Table 5.

Table 5. Learning Strategies used with Instructional Media

n=40 Teachers of English

Learning Strategies used with Instructional Media	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Spaced Practice	21	52.5
Retrieval Practice	30	75
Elaboration	33	82.5
Interleaving	35	87.5
Concrete Examples	34	85
Dual Coding	35	87.5

Table 5 depicted that 21 (52.5%), 30 (75%), 33 (82.5%), 35 (87.5%), 34 (85%) and 35 (87.5%) teachers used spaced practice, retrieval practice, elaboration, interleaving, concrete examples and dual coding learning strategies respectively. Teachers used spaced practice learning strategy whereby studying took place in small chunks over time, to enhance durable learning in the classroom. They assisted learners to create a studying calendar to plan out how to review chunks of content and carved out small chunks of class time every day for review. This strategy dexterously integrated English language and Oral Literature thus made learning process enjoyable and enriching for the learners. These results were in line with Mwangi, Kisirikoi, Gichema and Mukunga (2018) observations.

Through retrieval practice learning strategy, teachers implied that learners practised bringing information to mind without the help of e-material. Teachers instructed them to turn off their technological tools, and then led them to write everything they learnt about a particular term or topic or share their thoughts in a think – pair – share. When the practice was done, students checked their understanding by revisiting their materials and later discussed misconception as a class. Once they learnt how to do this in classrooms, they then applied it in the curriculum.

Elaboration learning strategy involved explaining and describing ideas with many details. It allowed learners to go beyond simple recall of information and start to make connections within the content. Students asked amongst themselves open – ended questions about the material, answered in as much detail as possible, then checked the materials to make sure their understanding was correct. This strategy was commonly used in Literature/Oral Literature. Whereas in concrete examples learning strategy, teachers used concrete examples when teaching abstract concepts, then asked learners to come up with their own, corrected any examples that is not quite right, and searched for more.

The teachers pointed out that interleaving learning strategy involved switch between ideas while studying. As well as, to learn a skill learner practised it over and over again but they learnt it more effectively if mixed the practice of it with other skills. It was revealed that experienced teachers taught the four language skills simultaneously as the learners automatically engaged in listening; acquiring speaking skills as they observed speakers; as well as reading and writing skills through the texts accompanying sounds and images. Though, dual coding learning strategy combined words and visuals in learning of English language. This process reinforced concepts in the brain through two different paths; this made it easier to retrieve it. To sum up, the aforementioned results were in tandem with Gonzalez (2016) observations. Conversely, Gonzalez focused on six powerful learning strategies shared with students.

According to the study, instructional media methods included teacher – learner interactive (mixed), learner – centred and teacher – centred. Instructional media provided high quality visual and auditory materials; but, the justification for their use should not just be that they match a single learning style. Instructional media methods for classroom use must be decided in advance; not during teaching and

learning process. Subsequently, PQ sought to find out from principals instructional media methods used in learning of English language. The findings were summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Instructional Media Methods used in Learning of English Language

n=20 Principals

Instructional Media Methods used in Learning	Number of Principals (<i>f</i>)	Percentages (%)
Learner - centred method	7	35
Teacher – learner interactive (Mixed) method	10	50
Teacher – centred method	3	15
Total	20	100.0

Table 6 showed that 10 (50%), 7 (35%) and 3 (15%) principals suggested that teachers used teacher – learner interactive, learner – centred and teacher – centred methods in learning of English language respectively. The abovementioned results demonstrated that teacher – learner interactive method was the most effective method, followed by learner – centred method while teacher – centred method was the least effective teaching method.

Teacher – centred method inhibited interactive learning in the classroom. Both teacher – learner interactive and learner – centred methods enhanced academic self-confidence, learner to learner and learner to teacher connectedness during learning process. Yet, interactive learning produced desirable learning outcomes in education. The study of Ganyaupfu (2013) concurred with the results in Table 2. Nevertheless, he investigated the differential effectiveness of teaching methods on students’ academic performance. He sampled 109 undergraduate students and used inferential statistics course; students’ assessment test scores were derived from the internal class test prepared by the lecturer. The differential effectiveness of the three teaching methods on student academic performance was analysed using the General Linear Model based univariate ANOVA technique.

ETQ sought to find out various instructional media methods used in learning of English language. The findings were summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Instructional Media Methods used in Learning Process

n=40 Teachers of English

Instructional Media Methods	Number of Teachers (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Learner – centred method	16	40
Teacher – learner Interactive method	20	50
Teacher – centred method	4	10
Total	40	100.0

Table 7 indicated that 16 (40), 20 (50) and 4 (10%) teachers used learner – centred, teacher – learner interactive and teacher – centred methods in learning of English language respectively. Teachers enjoyed using both learner – centred and teacher – learner interactive methods in learning process. These methods used discussions, role plays, debates, hot seat, question and answer activities. They involved hands – on, minds – on and heart – on activities that stirred up learner’s interests in learning process. They also provided learner’s needs such as stimulation, order (organisation of concepts), strategy (elaboration and mental imagery) and meaning (feedback and meaningfulness). The use of task driven instructional approach in education produced positive learning outcomes unlike teacher – centred instruction. For this reason, teaching methods supported with media improved students’ learning outcomes. The above mentioned observations were in tandem with Zhao, Wei and Yu-Sheng (2021) research. But, they focused on innovative pedagogy and designed - based research on flipped learning in higher education. They used evaluation framework to evaluate learning performance.

Besides, professional documents are used by teachers in preparation, implementation and evaluation of teaching and learning process. They include schemes of work, lesson plans, record of work, progress reports and Individualized Education Program (IEP). They are vital documents that a teacher use to keep track of his or her work, that of the learners as well as to make teaching and learning effective. Observation Schedule sought to find out instructional media methods used in professional documents. Findings summed up in Table 8.

Table 8. Instructional Media Methods used in Professional Documents

n=20 Teachers of English

Instructional Media Methods in Professional Documents	Number of Teachers (<i>f</i>)	Percentages (%)
Teacher – learner Interactive Method	11	55
Learner – centred Method	8	40
Teacher – centred Method	1	5
Total	20	100.0

Table 8 suggested that 11 (55%), 8 (40%) and 1 (5%) teachers used teacher-learner interactive, learner – centred and teacher – centred methods in professional documents respectively. Both teacher – learner interactive and learner – centred methods enhanced collaborative learning, inquiry – based learning, problem – based learning and project – based learning. Thus, student - centred teaching strategies improved teacher/learner relationships, critical thinking, enjoyment, interdependence, one another’s successes, group processing and individual/group accountability amongst learners. They enhanced participatory learning which made learners to discover their own capabilities and expertise through cooperative effort and exchange of knowledge. Respondents suggested that learner – centred and teacher – centred methods should be integrated to improve learning outcomes in the curriculum. Likewise, the results revealed that in teacher – learner interactive method the subject information produced by learners was remembered better than the same information presented to the learners by the teacher. Thus, teacher-centred method was least practical, theoretical and involved memorization.

Learner’s Questionnaire (LQ) sought to find out from learners instructional media methods used in learning of English language. The findings were summarized in Table 9.

Table 9. Instructional Media Methods used in Learning Process

n=500 Form Two learners

Instructional Media Methods used in Learning Process	Number of Learners (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Teacher – learner Interactive Method	253	50.6
Learner – centred Method	206	41.2
Teacher – centred Method	41	8.2
Total	500	100.00

In Table 9, 253 (50.6%), 206 (41.2%) and 41 (8.2%) learners suggested that teacher – learner interactive, learner – centred and teacher – centred methods were used in learning of English language respectively. Learners preferred teacher – learner interactive method in learning process. Thus, blended teaching methods encouraged self-learning and discovery learning process. They motivated learners to contribute in activities such discussion, debates, dialogues and role plays either through verbally or in written form. These results concurred with the research of Saeed, Ejaz and Rupert (2017); however, it was a comparison study. They collected data via semi – structured questionnaires distributed to undergraduate students from three countries: United Kingdom, Saudi Arabia and Kenya. Their study determined influence of online resources on student – lecturer relationship in higher education.

In teacher – centred method, respondents revealed that attention was concentrated on the teacher. Teachers were in charge of the classroom and directed all activities. Therefore, learners did not get the chance to direct and play an active role in learning of English language. Life skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, cooperation and debate were harder to gain in a teacher – centred classroom. It also reinforced traditional practices such as chalkboard and teaching – talking tradition.

Learner – centred method turned the focus on learners rather than on the teacher. In this approach, learners were allowed to use small groups, access centres and possibly move about in the language classroom freely. As a result, the method instilled a sense of responsibility in learners. They learnt internal/intrinsic motivation which built self confidence and created a lifelong love of learning in learners. Summarily, learners indicated that both teacher – learner interactive method and learner - centred method enhanced positive learning outcomes in the curriculum.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

School administrators must encourage teachers to use teacher – learner interactive method and learner – centred method supported with instructional media in learning of English language. These methods use learner-centred teaching/learning strategies which produced positive learning outcomes in the curriculum.

Policy Recommendations

Teachers should use learner – centred teaching/learning strategies in education because they produced positive learning outcomes in the curriculum. These strategies reinforced use of teacher-learner interactive method and learner-centred method incorporated with instructional media in the classrooms.

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